

Mammal Expedition on Kenya's North Coast: Biodiversity Assessment and Training of Early-Career Mammalogists

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ABSTRACT

From 29 May to 3 June 2025, the Mammal Committee of Nature Kenya and the Mammalogy Section of the National Museums of Kenya conducted a multidisciplinary field expedition to northern coastal Kenya aimed at building capacity in mammal identification and distribution mapping, contributing occurrence records to the *Mammals of Kenya Atlas* (MaKenya) and iNaturalist, and assessing threats to regional biodiversity. Eight participants (four students and four researchers/naturalists) surveyed ecosystems ranging from dry savannas to coastal forests and documented 55 mammal species, including three Critically Endangered, five Endangered, six Vulnerable, and five Near Threatened taxa, with the remainder listed as Least Concern. All mammal records were submitted to MaKenya, while additional records of mammals and other taxa were contributed to iNaturalist. The survey identified major threats to biodiversity, including agricultural expansion that is further restricting the already limited ranges of the Critically Endangered Tana River primates and the Endangered coastal topi, overgrazing by livestock, the spread of invasive species—most notably *Prosopis juliflora* (“mathenge”)—insufficient formal protection for threatened species outside protected areas, infrastructure development such as newly paved roads that increase roadkill incidence, and inadequate conservation funding. In contrast, positive community-based conservation initiatives were observed, particularly the leadership of Somali communities in conserving the Critically Endangered hirola. Overall, the expedition generated critical distributional data, provided hands-on training for early-career naturalists, strengthened collaborative monitoring of Kenya’s mammal fauna, and underscored the importance of documenting endangered and endemic mammals to guide effective conservation planning.

INTRODUCTION

Kenya is characterized by a remarkable diversity of ecosystems that together support nearly 400 mammal species (Kingdon et al., 2013). The country's major biomes include tropical montane forests, savannah grasslands, arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs), coastal forests and mangroves, and wetlands and riparian habitats (Mwangi et al., 2016). Each biome harbors distinctive mammalian fauna adapted to specific ecological conditions. For instance, savannah ecosystems support iconic species such as elephants (*Loxodonta africana*), lions (*Panthera leo*), and giraffes (*Giraffa reticulata* and *Giraffa tippelskirchi*), while the montane forests of Mount Kenya and the Aberdares are home to rare and endemic species such as the bongo (*Tragelaphus eurycerus*) and the Mount Kenya vlei rat (*Otomys orestes*) (Fashing et al., 2014). Along the Indian Ocean coast, forests and mangroves sustain unique small mammals, including the Endangered golden-rumped sengi (*Rhynchocyon chrysopygus*) and the Kenya coast galago (*Paragalago cocos*) (Howard et al., 2017).

The northern coastal region of Kenya—including Lamu, Garissa, and Tana River counties—contains a mosaic of habitats comprising coastal forests, mangrove swamps, riverine forests, arid bushlands, and savannas (Mwangi et al., 2016; Howard et al., 2017). These landscapes harbor globally significant populations of threatened species, including the Critically Endangered hirola (*Beatragus hunteri*; Butynski, 2000; Andanje et al., 2011), Tana River red colobus (*Piliocolobus rufomitratu*s; Wieczkowski, 2005), and Tana River mangabey (*Cercocebus galeritus*; Mbora & Meikle, 2004). The Endangered coastal topi (*Damaliscus lunatus topi*; East, 1999) and reticulated giraffe (*Giraffa reticulata*; Muneza et al., 2016), as well as other taxa such as the golden-rumped sengi (IUCN SSC Afrotheria Specialist Group, 2016) and the Kenya coast galago, further underscore the region's exceptional conservation value.

Despite this importance, biodiversity data from northern coastal Kenya remain patchy, limiting effective conservation planning. This gap is particularly concerning given mounting threats, including habitat degradation from agricultural expansion and livestock overstocking, infrastructure development such as newly paved roads, the spread of invasive species like *Prosopis juliflora*, and insufficient funding and enforcement for conservation outside protected areas (KWS, 2020; Scofield et al., 2019). These challenges are compounded by limited technical

capacity in mammalogy and biodiversity monitoring (Mwangi et al., 2016). In response, emerging initiatives provide new opportunities for conservation action. Citizen science platforms such as the MaKenya Mammal App and iNaturalist enable students, researchers, and local communities to contribute occurrence records, generating real-time biodiversity data while fostering public engagement (Bonney et al., 2016; Mwangi et al., 2019; iNaturalist, 2023). Complementing these data-driven efforts, community-led conservation plays a critical role, exemplified by Somali pastoralists' long-standing stewardship of the world's most endangered antelope, the Critically Endangered hirola.

Building on these emerging conservation initiatives and in response to urgent data gaps, the Mammal Committee of Nature Kenya, in partnership with the National Museums of Kenya, organized a multidisciplinary field expedition from 29 May to 3 June 2025 with the objectives of building capacity in mammal identification and distribution mapping, contributing occurrence records to the Mammals of Kenya Atlas (MaKenya) and iNaturalist, and assessing threats to biodiversity in the region.

METHODS

Observations were conducted opportunistically along transects across community lands, private farms, conservancies, and protected areas using binoculars, field guides, and handheld GPS units. All mammal records, including live sightings and roadkill, were documented with the time, date, geographic location, and group composition where applicable. Data were uploaded to the MaKenya mobile application and the iNaturalist online platform. Participants received hands-on training in mammal identification, standardized data recording, and the ecological context of field observations.

Figure 1: Transect route (indicated in red) along which field surveys were conducted, starting in Nairobi and proceeding through Garissa, Ishaqbin, Tana River Primate Reserve, Mida Creek, and Gede Ruins, then continuing to Tsavo East and Tsavo West, and finally returning to Nairobi.

RESULTS

Day 1, 29 May: Nairobi to Garissa:

The expedition began with a 370 km journey from Nairobi to Garissa, traversing a mosaic of urban centers, cultivated landscapes, and semi-arid scrublands. Despite the ecological heterogeneity along this route, mammal sightings were scarce, an unsurprising outcome given the extensive habitat disturbance and high human activity along the corridor. Only two mammal records were documented, one of which was a roadkill, highlighting the increasing impact of expanding road networks on wildlife movement and survival.

Figure 2: Roadkill record of a striped hyaena (*Hyaena hyaena*), an elusive and primarily nocturnal scavenger listed as Near Threatened by the IUCN. This observation highlights the impacts of road development through wildlife habitats and underscores the need for wildlife-sensitive road planning to reduce mortality and habitat fragmentation.

Mammals observed

1. Striped hyaena (*Hyaena hyaena*; Near Threatened) – Roadkill observed at Beneneka
2. White-tailed mongoose (*Ichneumia albicauda*; Least Concern) – Sighted in Garissa town

Day 2, 30 May: Garissa to Masalani:

The 205 km stretch between Garissa and Masalani traverses a semi-arid landscape dominated by thorny bushland and open savannah. Natural vegetation is characterized by drought-resistant taxa such as *Acacia*, *Commiphora*, and *Combretum*, interspersed with grassy plains and seasonal pans that retain water during the rains. However, native vegetation is increasingly threatened by the aggressive spread of *Prosopis juliflora* (commonly known as mathenge), an invasive shrub originally introduced for land reclamation and erosion control. The species now proliferates widely, outcompeting indigenous flora, degrading pasturelands, and altering habitat structure.

Along this route, we observed numerous crows scavenging along the road, particularly between Kafi Junction and Hola Junction, where we recorded at least five roadkills. Several carcasses were partially consumed, leaving dried remains on the asphalt. Notable records included a freshly killed African civet (*Civettictis civetta*), a Cape hare (*Lepus capensis*), and a ground

squirrel, as well as desiccated remains of another civet, collectively underscoring the substantial toll of vehicle collisions on local wildlife.

Despite these sobering observations, the journey also revealed pockets of thriving wildlife. We encountered two troops of yellow baboons (*Papio cynocephalus*), both with infants clinging to their mothers, as well as common warthogs (*Phacochoerus africanus*) accompanied by piglets foraging near the roadside. Most memorably, several flocks of vulturine guineafowl (*Acryllium vulturinum*) moved across the dusty landscape in coordinated formations. Their striking blue plumage and synchronized movements provided a vivid reminder of the resilience and biodiversity that persist even within harsh and human-impacted environments.

Figure 3: Along the Kafi Junction–Hola Junction road, life and loss occur side by side: yellow baboons (*Papio cynocephalus*) with dependent young and a solitary common warthog (*Phacochoerus africanus*) pause at the roadside, while nearby the remains of a Cape hare (*Lepus capensis*) and an African civet (*Civettictis civetta*) lie on the tarmac. These contrasting scenes underscore the often-unseen toll that roads impose on wildlife moving through semi-arid landscapes.

Figure 4: Flocks of vulturine guineafowl (*Acryllium vulturinum*) observed along the dry stretch between Garissa and Masalani. The species' striking blue plumage and coordinated group movements contrasted sharply with the surrounding arid landscape, illustrating the persistence of visually and ecologically distinctive wildlife within semi-arid environments.

Mammals observed

1. Common warthog (*Phacochoerus africanus*; Least Concern) – 10 individuals observed between Haramasi and Chairende
2. Yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*; Least Concern) – Two groups observed along the roadside
3. Common civet (*Civettictis civetta*; Least Concern) – Observed as roadkill
4. Cape hare (*Lepus capensis*; Least Concern) – Observed as roadkill
5. Unstriped ground squirrel (*Xerus rutilus*; Least Concern) – Observed at Hola
6. Plains zebra (*Equus quagga*; Near Threatened) – Herd observed in Masalani
7. Desert warthog (*Phacochoerus aethiopicus*; Least Concern) – Several individuals observed in Masalani town

Day 2 & 3, 30 May- 31 May: Ishaqbin Hirola Community Conservancy

Our visit to the Ishaqbini Hirola Community Conservancy began in Masalani town, where we were received by the conservancy manager and provided with a detailed briefing on ongoing conservation efforts for one of the world's most endangered antelopes, the hirola (*Beatragus hunteri*). Established in 2005 and located in Ijara Sub-county, Garissa County, the conservancy covers approximately 240 km² along the eastern bank of the Tana River and encompasses the communities of Kotile, Korisa, Hara, and Abaratilo (Measham & Lumbasi 2013; Ali et al. 2018). Within the conservancy lies a 25 km² predator-proof sanctuary, established in 2012 to serve as a secure breeding area for the hirola (Ali et al. 2018). The area contains a mosaic of habitats, including acacia bushlands, savannah grasslands, riverine forests, and seasonal floodplains, supporting high levels of biodiversity in an otherwise arid landscape.

Following the briefing, we travelled from Masalani to the sanctuary and spent the afternoon surveying internal tracks in search of hirola. Although the species remained elusive during initial surveys, we recorded several other mammals, including Kirk's dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*), reticulated giraffe (*Giraffa reticulata*), desert warthog (*Phacochoerus aethiopicus*), lesser kudu (*Tragelaphus imberbis*), vervet monkey (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*), and yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*). We were also introduced to a rescued juvenile gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*), currently under the care of the conservancy after being found orphaned, illustrating the close involvement of local communities in wildlife stewardship.

Surveys resumed at dawn the following morning, when repeated slow transects eventually allowed prolonged observation and photographic documentation of a hirola herd within the sanctuary. Observing these Critically Endangered antelopes within their last stronghold, maintained through community-led conservation, highlighted the effectiveness of locally driven protection efforts. After exiting the sanctuary, we continued into the broader conservancy towards Lake Ishaqbini, a seasonal oxbow lake near the Tana River, where vegetation shifted markedly from thorny scrub to dense riverine and coastal forest. The area supports high primate diversity, and for many participants, a key highlight was the first confirmed observation of the endemic Critically Endangered Tana River red colobus (*Piliocolobus rufomitratu*s).

Throughout our time at Ishaqbini, we observed both the challenges and innovations associated with wildlife management in arid environments. Selective cutting of dense acacia thickets was evident across the landscape; a targeted management strategy aimed at promoting grass regeneration and improving forage availability for grazers such as the hirola. Discussions with conservancy staff also revealed ongoing financial challenges, including recent funding reductions that have affected staffing and operational capacity. Despite these constraints, strong local support for conservation persists. In surrounding villages, wildlife such as warthogs and zebras were frequently observed resting near homesteads, reflecting a high degree of tolerance and coexistence between people and wildlife in the region.

Mammals observed

1. Hirola (*Beatragus hunteri*; **Critically Endangered**) – Seven individuals observed in the Ishaqbini Sanctuary
2. Desert warthog (*Phacochoerus aethiopicus*; Least Concern) – Several individuals observed in the sanctuary
3. Kirk's dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*; Least Concern) – Several individuals observed in the sanctuary
4. Gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*; **Near Threatened**) – Several individuals observed in the sanctuary, including a rescued fawn under care
5. Vervet monkey (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*; Least Concern) – Observed around Ishaqbini Sanctuary close to the offices as well as at Lake Ishaqbin
6. Yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*; Least Concern) – Observed near the dam within the sanctuary and huge troops of about 40 scattered in open field with massive low standing trees
7. Lesser kudu (*Tragelaphus imberbis*; Near Threatened) – Observed in the sanctuary
8. Reticulated giraffe (*Giraffa reticulata*; **Endangered**) – Approximately 15 individuals observed within the sanctuary
9. Tana River red colobus (*Piliocolobus rufomitratu*s; **Critically Endangered**) – Three individuals observed at Lake Ishaqbini
10. Coastal Sykes' monkey (*Cercopithecus mitis albotorquatus*; Vulnerable) – Eight individuals observed at Lake Ishaqbini
11. African buffalo (*Syncerus caffer*; Least Concern) – Fresh tracks observed at Lake Ishaqbini

12. Impala (*Aepyceros melampus*; Least Concern) – Observed within the sanctuary
13. African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*; **Endangered**) – Presence indicated by fresh dung within the sanctuary
14. Plains zebra (*Equus quagga*; Near Threatened) – Observed en route to Ishaqbini Sanctuary
15. Lion (*Panthera leo*; Vulnerable) – Reported by Ishaqbini's head of research as present in the conservancy
16. Leopard (*Panthera pardus*; Vulnerable) – Also reported in the conservancy by the head of research
17. Coastal topi (*Damaliscus lunatus topi*; Near Threatened) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
18. Waterbuck (*Kobus ellipsiprymnus*; Least Concern; defassa subspecies Near Threatened) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
19. Black-tailed gerbil (*Gerbilliscus nigricaudus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
20. Black-backed jackal (*Lupulella mesomelas*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
21. Common genet (*Genetta genetta*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
22. Cape hare (*Lepus capensis*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
23. Small-eared galago (*Otolemur garnettii*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
24. Senegal lesser galago (*Galago senegalensis*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
25. Somali dwarf mongoose (*Helogale hirtula*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
26. African civet (*Civettictis civetta*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy
27. Unstriped ground squirrel (*Xerus rutilus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within the conservancy

Figure 5: Two hirola (*Beatragus hunteri*), the world's most endangered antelope and listed as Critically Endangered by the IUCN, observed standing alert within a clearing in the Ishaqbini Sanctuary. The individuals were oriented in opposite directions, a vigilance behavior typical of the species. For many expedition participants, this represented a first confirmed encounter with the hirola and highlights the effectiveness of sustained community-led conservation efforts at Ishaqbini.

Figure 6: On the left, Leo Khasoha, Chairperson of the Mammal Committee of Nature Kenya, gently holds a rescued juvenile gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*). On the right, the young antelope stands independently within Ishaqbini Sanctuary, where it is being nurtured on goat milk after being found orphaned by local herders. The images reflect the compassion and commitment underpinning community-led conservation efforts in the region.

Figure 7: Cleared acacia branches scattered across the ground within Ishaqbini Sanctuary, reflecting a targeted vegetation management practice aimed at reducing dense thickets and promoting grass regeneration. This intervention improves forage availability for the Critically Endangered hirola (*Beatragus hunteri*) and other grazing species and illustrates the application of locally informed management strategies in community-led conservation.

Figure 8: Top left: Coastal Sykes' monkey (*Cercopithecus mitis albatorquatus*), also known as Pousargues's monkey, observed within the forest canopy. Top right: A Tana River red colobus (*Piliocolobus rufomitratu*), one of the world's most endangered primates, sheltering with a dependent infant during a rainy morning, partially concealed within the upper canopy. Bottom: Lake Ishaqbini, a seasonal oxbow lake surrounded by remnant coastal forest, providing critical habitat for these and numerous other species within the community-managed Ishaqbini Conservancy.

Figure 9: Top left: Desert warthogs (*Phacochoerus aethiopicus*) feeding near a homestead within the Ishaqbini Conservancy, illustrating tolerance and coexistence between wildlife and local communities. Top right: A male and female yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*) moving through an open field with scattered fallen tree trunks; the individuals displayed affiliative and courtship-related behaviors at the edge of a human-modified landscape. Bottom left: A black-faced sandgrouse (*Pterocles decoratus*) standing on a sanctuary road, showing limited avoidance behavior toward vehicles. Bottom right: A white-bellied bustard (*Lissotis tachiro*) moving through scrub habitat, highlighting the diversity of birdlife supported within the conservancy.

Day 3, 31 May: Ishaqbini Conservancy-Ngumu-Minjila- Garsen

Departing Ishaqbini Conservancy, we travelled toward Kotile through a landscape characterized by sparse human settlement interspersed with active wildlife use. Around Kotile, the habitat was dominated by semi-arid woodland, with *Dobera glabra* emerging as a defining species. *Dobera* is a much-branched evergreen tree adapted to saline and calcareous soils in lowland dry areas, reaching up to 8 m in height and characterized by thick grey-green leaves and small ovoid fruits. Although not a preferred browse for wildlife or livestock, its leaves may be used as drought fodder, while its fruits and seeds serve as an important emergency food for humans during famine periods when properly processed. The species also provides shade, firewood, and material for household implements and traditional toothbrushes. Ecologically, its presence indicates resilient dryland woodland with access to subsurface water and reflects long-term coexistence with pastoral land use (Ruffo et al., 2002).

Within this woodland, we encountered two herds of coastal topi (*Damaliscus lunatus topi*), both accompanied by young calves. The herds watched briefly before moving deeper into the bush. The coastal topi is listed as Endangered on the IUCN Red List and has a highly fragmented distribution in coastal Kenya and southern Somalia, with declines driven by habitat loss, competition with livestock, and hunting (East, 1999). Observations of breeding herds in this area were therefore unexpected and encouraging, suggesting that this stretch of habitat retains important ecological value. The topi were observed alongside plains zebra (*Equus quagga*), yellow baboons (*Papio cynocephalus*), warthogs (*Phacochoerus* spp.), and a small number of giraffes, forming a diverse assemblage within the *Dobera*-dominated landscape.

Continuing from Kotile toward Lazima, vegetation gradually transitioned into denser thorn-scrub. Flaky thorn (*Vachellia exuvialis*) became increasingly common, accompanied by umbrella thorn acacia (*Acacia tortilis*), African myrrh (*Commiphora africana*), green-berry tree (*Boscia coriacea*), and the toothbrush tree (*Salvadora persica*). Occasional desert date (*Balanites aegyptiaca*) and flowering desert rose (*Adenium obesum*) added structural and visual diversity to the landscape. Wildlife observations declined in this zone, with only occasional vervet monkeys (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*), Kirk's dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*), and gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*) recorded, while large wild grazers were largely absent. Instead, substantial herds of domestic goats dominated the area.

Approaching Lazima and the Tana River floodplain, signs of human settlement and cultivation increased markedly, including fenced fields, homesteads, and irrigated plots. This marked a clear socio-ecological transition from sparsely populated rangelands around Kotile to the river-fed, human-dominated floodplain ecosystems of the lower Tana River basin (Maingi & Marsh, 2002).

Mammals observed

1. Reticulated giraffe (*Giraffa reticulata*; **Endangered**) – Approximately 5 individuals observed near Kotile
2. Plains zebra (*Equus quagga*; Near Threatened) – Observed en route to around Kotile
3. Coastal topi (*Damaliscus lunatus topi*; Near Threatened) – two groups of 5 and 7 observed near Kotile

4. Gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*; **Near Threatened**) – two individuals observed feeding in the thickets around Kotile
5. Somali dwarf mongoose (*Helogale hirtula*) – a group of approximately seven observed running in and out what appeared like a low termite mound
6. Kirk's dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*; Least Concern) – a few individuals observed in the thickets in between Kotile and Lazima
7. Vervet monkey (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*; Least Concern) – a group of five individuals observed crossing the road and hanging around the road between Kotile and Lazima
8. Yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*; Least Concern) – Observed near Lazima area and along Tana River Delta feeding in the farms

Figure 10: Top left: A small group of coastal topi (*Damaliscus lunatus topi*), including a dependent calf, observed alert within *Dobera glabra*-dominated woodland near Kotile before moving deeper into cover. Bottom left: A plains zebra (*Equus quagga*) retreating into surrounding thorn scrub. Right: Flowering desert rose (*Adenium obesum*) within the semi-arid landscape, illustrating the botanical diversity characteristic of this dryland habitat.

Figure 11: Coastal topi (*Damaliscus lunatus topi*) observed alert among *Dobera glabra* stumps within semi-arid woodland near Kotile, with freshly regenerated grasses following recent rains. Locally known among Somali communities as Garas, Dobera woodlands provide important habitat structure within this landscape. The coastal topi, an Endangered subspecies with a fragmented range in coastal Kenya and southern Somalia, was a notable highlight of the expedition and represented a first confirmed sighting for several participants.

Figure 12: Flaky thorn (*Vachellia exuvialis*) dominating the thorn-scrub landscape between Kotile and Lazima, characterized by its distinctive peeling bark. This hardy species forms a key structural component of the vegetation community, occurring alongside umbrella thorn acacia (*Acacia tortilis*), African myrrh (*Commiphora africana*), and the toothbrush tree (*Salvadora persica*), all adapted to the dry-season conditions of this semi-arid environment.

Day 3, 31 May: Tana River Primate National Reserve

Our visit to the Tana River Primate National Reserve began along the Garsen–Hola road, where the surrounding landscape was characterized by open, semi-arid bushland. Vegetation in this outer zone consisted of widely spaced umbrella thorn (*Acacia tortilis*), black hook-thorn (*Senegalia mellifera*), *Commiphora* shrubs, and scattered baobabs (*Adansonia digitata*), with sparse ground cover dominated by drought-tolerant grasses and low shrubs. Wildlife observations in this zone were limited and included Kirk’s dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*), gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*), and extensive livestock grazing, reflecting strong human influence at the reserve periphery.

As we progressed deeper into the reserve, the bushland gradually became denser and more structurally complex. This transitional zone featured increased acacia cover, occasional stands of toothbrush tree (*Salvadora persica*), and fruiting shrubs, likely benefiting from seasonal flooding

Conservation Context of the Tana River Mangabey and Tana River Red Colobus

The Tana River red colobus (*Ptilocolobus rufomitratu*s) and the Tana River mangabey (*Cercocebus gal*eritus) are both listed as **Critically Endangered** on the IUCN Red List and are endemic to a narrow stretch of riverine forest along the lower Tana River in southeastern Kenya. These species are found nowhere else in the world, with their entire global distribution restricted to approximately 60 km of fragmented gallery forest, most of which lies within or adjacent to the Tana River Primate National Reserve. As forest specialists, both primates depend on intact riparian forests that track the meandering river and are sustained by seasonal flooding.

This critical hydrological system is increasingly threatened by large-scale upstream water infrastructure. In particular, dam development along the Tana River, including the High Grand Falls Dam currently under construction, has altered the natural flood regime that maintains soil moisture, groundwater recharge, and forest regeneration. Reduced flood frequency and intensity lead to drying of forest soils, lower recruitment of key tree species, and progressive degradation of primate habitat (Butynski & Hamerlynck, 2016; Maingi et al., 2020).

Habitat loss and degradation are further compounded by human pressures. Riparian forests are cleared for subsistence agriculture, settlement, and livestock grazing, while illegal cutting of fig trees for canoe construction and harvesting of wild date palms—an important food resource for primates—further diminish habitat quality. Additional stressors include wildfire, regional insecurity, and increasing human–wildlife conflict, particularly as mangabeys are persecuted for crop raiding when natural food availability declines (Wieczkowski & Butynski, 2013).

Despite the reserve’s formal protected status, limited enforcement capacity, persistent insecurity, and a past court ruling that challenged the reserve’s legal standing have left these forests highly vulnerable. Without urgent, coordinated conservation action that integrates hydrological management, habitat protection, and community engagement, the long-term persistence of both the Tana River mangabey and Tana River red colobus remains uncertain (Butynski & de Jong, 2019).

and improved soil moisture. Although still semi-arid in character, this zone marked a clear ecological gradient toward the riverine system and a noticeable shift in habitat quality.

The transition into riverine forest was abrupt and striking. Dense, shaded gallery forest developed immediately adjacent to the Tana River, dominated by wild date palm (*Phoenix reclinata*), fig trees (*Ficus* spp.), waterberries (*Syzygium* spp.), and *Barringtonia racemosa*. The forest understory was rich and humid, supported by deep alluvial soils deposited during seasonal floods. This narrow forest corridor represents the ecological core of the reserve and supports high faunal diversity relative to the surrounding drylands.

Guided by long-term researcher Charles Maingi, we conducted slow surveys within the riverine

forest. Wildlife observations included vervet monkeys (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*) and red colobus monkeys feeding in the canopy, as well as auditory and visual records of hippopotamus

(*Hippopotamus amphibius*) along the river. During the survey, multiple encounters with Tana River mangabeys (*Cercocebus galeritus*) were recorded, including individuals foraging on palm fruits and others moving rapidly through dense undergrowth upon detecting our presence. These observations confirmed active use of the forest interior by this Critically Endangered species.

Additional signs of mammal activity included fresh tracks of common duiker (*Sylvicapra grimmia*), underscoring the cryptic diversity present within the forest. Collectively, these observations highlighted the sharp ecological contrast between the arid rangelands surrounding the reserve and the narrow but highly productive riverine forest that sustains its unique mammal assemblage.

Figure 13: Left: A track leading into the dense riverine forest of the Tana River Primate National Reserve, marking entry into the core habitat of two Critically Endangered primates. Bottom left: Cinnabar bracket fungus (*Trametes sanguinea*) growing on a fallen log, illustrating active decomposition and nutrient cycling within the forest. Right: Riverine forest dominated by wild date palms (*Phoenix reclinata*) and fig trees (*Ficus* spp.) along the Tana River, whose seasonal flooding sustains this narrow but highly productive habitat supporting the endemic Tana River mangabey (*Cercocebus galeritus*) and Tana River red colobus (*Piliocolobus rufomitratu*s).

Figure 14: A female Tana River mangabey (*Cercocebus galeritus*) observed feeding on ripe palm fruit while perched on a fallen tree within the riverine forest of the Tana River Primate National Reserve. This encounter provided a clear visual record of the species' use of forest floor and fallen woody debris during foraging. The Tana River mangabey is listed as Critically Endangered on the IUCN Red List and is restricted to a narrow band of riverine forest along the lower Tana River.

Figure 15: A Tana River red colobus (*Piliocolobus rufomitratu*) observed perched within the forest canopy of the Tana River Primate National Reserve. The individual displayed the species' characteristic dark grey pelage with a reddish crown and paler ventral surface, features that provide effective camouflage within the dappled light of the riverine forest. The Tana River red colobus is listed as Critically Endangered on the IUCN Red List and is endemic to a narrow stretch of riparian forest along the lower Tana River.

Figure 16: A group of hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibius*) observed along the Tana River within the Tana River Primate National Reserve. Individuals were seen surfacing and submerging in the river channel, with others remaining partially submerged with eyes and ears exposed. These observations highlight the continued use of the riverine system by large semi-aquatic mammals within the reserve.

Mammals observed

1. Kirk's dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*; Least Concern) – a few individuals observed scamping around in the reserve
2. Vervet monkey (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*; Least Concern) – Observed along the Garsen-Hola road and within the reserve
3. Yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*; Least Concern) – Observed along the Garsen-Hola road
4. Tana River red colobus (*Piliocolobus rufomitratu*s; **Critically Endangered**) – several individuals observed along the forest stretch in the reserve
5. Coastal Sykes' monkey (*Cercopithecus mitis albotorquatus*; Vulnerable) – several individuals observed along the forest stretch in the reserve
6. Impala (*Aepyceros melampus*; Least Concern) – Observed within the reserve
7. African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*; **Endangered**) – Presence indicated by fresh dung in the forest stretch along River Tana

8. Bushbuck (*Tragelaphus scriptus*; Least Concern) – Tracks observed along the forest stretch in the reserve
9. Red-bellied bush squirrel (*Paraxerus palliatus*; Least Concern) – Observed climbing a palm tree
10. Senegal lesser galago (*Galago senegalensis*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur along the forest stretch
11. Large-spotted genet (*Genetta maculata*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within reserve
12. White-tailed mongoose (*Ichneumia albicauda*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within reserve
13. Harvey's duiker (*Cephalophus harveyi*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within reserve
14. Kenya coast dwarf galago (*Paragalago cocos*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within reserve
15. Northern greater galago-lasiotis (*Otolemur garnettii lasiotis*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within reserve

Day 4, 1 June: Mida Creek

We departed Garsen early in the morning and travelled approximately 115 km toward Malindi. This stretch of the journey passed through landscapes dominated by human settlements and cultivated land, with few visible wild mammals recorded. Approaching Malindi, the landscape shifted noticeably with the appearance of extensive salt-processing mounds associated with industrial salt extraction in the area. From Malindi, we continued south toward Watamu and arrived at Mida Creek, a tidal estuary within the Malindi–Watamu Biosphere Reserve.

At Mida Creek, we met with a field officer from A Rocha Kenya, a conservation organization engaged in biodiversity protection and sustainable development along the Kenyan coast. We were introduced to the Arabuko-Sokoke Schools and Ecotourism Scheme (ASSETS), a flagship community-based initiative that links conservation of Mida Creek and surrounding ecosystems with local livelihoods. The program uses revenue generated from ecotourism to support secondary school scholarships—benefiting 762 students to date—and promotes sustainable income-generating activities such as beekeeping and environmentally responsible fishing practices.

Ecologically, Mida Creek comprises a complex mosaic of habitats, including extensive mangrove forests, seagrass beds, mudflats, and tidal channels. The mangrove system supports nine species: *Rhizophora mucronata*, *Avicennia marina*, *Sonneratia alba*, *Bruguiera gymnorhiza*, *Ceriops tagal*, *Lumnitzera racemosa*, *Xylocarpus granatum*, *Xylocarpus moluccensis*, and *Heritiera littoralis* (Kairo et al., 2002; Bosire et al., 2006). The creek also includes important islands such as Kirepwe and Sudi, which are characterized by dense mangrove cover and serve as key roosting sites for waterbirds.

Although no wild mammals were directly observed during our visit, several species are known to occur in the area, including Sykes' monkeys (*Cercopithecus mitis*), yellow baboons (*Papio cynocephalus*), African civets (*Civettictis civetta*), and common duikers (*Sylvicapra grimmia*), with some populations reported from the mangrove islands that were not accessible during this survey. Overall, Mida Creek represents a critical coastal ecosystem where biodiversity conservation is closely integrated with community-based development and education initiatives (BirdLife International, 2023; Groom et al., 2012; UNEP, 2020).

Mammals Reported

1. Vervet monkey (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*; Least Concern) – Reported at the entrance area
2. Yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*; Least Concern) – Reported on the islands
3. Bush duiker (*Sylvicapra grimmia*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur
4. African civets (*Civettictis civetta*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur
5. Marsh mongoose (*Atilax paludinosus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur

Figure 17: From left to right: Leo Khasoha, Simon Musila, Rowan Hadege, John Kabue, Mercy Ndumia, Lawrence Lonyil, and Olivia Mukasia—participants in the mammal expedition—pictured at Mida Creek during a field discussion on coastal ecosystems within the Malindi–Watamu Biosphere Reserve.

Figure 18: Participants walking along a traditional wooden boardwalk through the mangrove forest at Mida Creek, illustrating access routes used for environmental education and highlighting the ecological importance of Kenya’s coastal wetland ecosystems.

Figure 19: Sacred ibises (*Threskiornis aethiopicus*) foraging in the shallow tidal waters of Mida Creek, probing compact sediments rich in crabs and other benthic invertebrates.

Day 4, 1 June: Gede Ruins

Following our visit to Mida Creek, we travelled to Gede Ruins with the primary objective of searching for the golden-rumped sengi (*Rhynchocyon chrysopygus*), a rare and Endangered mammal endemic to Kenya's coastal forests. Prior to beginning the survey, we met with Mr. Mwaringa, who leads the butterfly conservation program under the National Museums of Kenya. This community-based initiative links biodiversity conservation with sustainable livelihoods through butterfly farming for export, beekeeping, and environmental education, providing an important model for conservation-linked income generation.

The forest at Gede represents a small but significant remnant of coastal forest. The canopy was relatively open, with sparse understory vegetation, a forest floor dominated by dry leaf litter, and abundant signs of insect and arthropod activity. We also noted shallow digging marks in the soil, likely attributable to squirrels. Before commencing the search, Dr. Simon Musila briefed participants on survey strategies, noting that recent light rainfall had dampened the leaf litter and reduced insect activity. This likely lowered detection probability for sengis, which are often

located by the rustling sounds they make while foraging through dry leaves and by their characteristic tail-tapping behavior.

To improve coverage, the group split into three smaller teams and searched different sections of the forest simultaneously. Initial efforts were unsuccessful, though several hedgehogs were encountered curled into defensive postures, providing notable observations. Sykes' monkeys (*Cercopithecus mitis*) were also active in the canopy, and their sudden movements occasionally mimicked the rapid motion expected of a sengi on the forest floor. Eventually, one team briefly sighted a golden-rumped sengi as it dashed through the leaf litter at high speed. Although only one participant observed the animal, the sighting confirmed the species' continued presence within the forest fragment. Despite further targeted searching, the individual was not relocated.

Local informants indicated that illegal trapping remains an ongoing threat to sengis in the area. Combined with the small size of the forest fragment, its proximity to human settlements, and visible signs of disturbance—including household waste dumping, plastic and diaper litter, and open defecation along forest edges—the long-term persistence of the species at Gede remains uncertain. The visit concluded with a walk through the Gede historical ruins, underscoring the close juxtaposition of cultural heritage and contemporary conservation challenges within this fragile coastal ecosystem.

Mammals Reported

1. Vervet monkey (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*; Least Concern) – Observed 10 individuals at the entrance area
2. Sykes monkey (*Cercopithecus mitis*; Least Concern) – Observed 15 individuals both at the entrance and in the forest
3. Golden-rumped sengi (*Rhynchocyon chrysopygus*; Endangered) – Observed one individual
4. White-bellied hedgehog (*Erinaceus concolor*; Least Concern) – Observed two individuals in the forest

Figure 20: A hedgehog (*Atelerix albiventris*) observed curled into a defensive posture on the forest floor within the coastal forest patch at Gede Ruins, illustrating a common anti-predator strategy among small mammals.

Day 5, 2 June: Malindi-Tsavo East National Park (via Sala Gate)

We departed Malindi at 05:30 h under cool early-morning conditions and travelled inland toward Tsavo East National Park via Sala Gate. The initial section of the route, from Malindi through Ganda and Kakuyuni, retained a strong coastal character, with landscapes dominated by coconut palms (*Cocos nucifera*), cashew trees, cultivated plots, and coastal thickets interspersed with roadside shrubs, including wild sage (*Lantana camara*). As we progressed toward Kakoneni, vegetation gradually thinned, giving way to drier conditions characterized by stunted *Acacia* and *Commiphora* shrubs, reduced cultivation, and increasingly dusty soils.

Beyond Lango Baya, the landscape transitioned into classic *Acacia*–*Commiphora* bushland, with umbrella thorn (*Acacia tortilis*) and African myrrh (*Commiphora africana*) dominating. Desert date (*Balanites aegyptiaca*), toothbrush tree (*Salvadora persica*), and numerous termite mounds marked the increasingly arid terrain. Approaching Makongeni, the environment became markedly drier, with doum palms (*Hyphaene compressa*) lining dry riverbeds and signs of human settlement becoming sparse. Near the Galana River, just before Sala Gate, the scenery

shifted abruptly to a narrow riparian strip dominated by tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*), sycamore fig (*Ficus sycomorus*), and dense palms, creating a striking contrast with the surrounding thorn scrub.

Upon entering Tsavo East National Park, the first approximately 20 km beyond Sala Gate revealed heavily degraded habitat, with extensive bare ground, sparse vegetation, and mature flame trees (*Delonix elata*) showing clear signs of intense elephant browsing. Roughly 10 km farther into the park, vegetation structure improved noticeably, with grass cover increasing, shrubs returning, and taller trees providing shade and raptor perches. Correspondingly, wildlife observations increased substantially. Large herbivores recorded included hartebeest (*Alcelaphus buselaphus*), impala (*Aepyceros melampus*), Grant's gazelle (*Nanger granti*), fringe-eared oryx (*Oryx beisa callotis*), plains zebra (*Equus quagga*), common eland (*Taurotragus oryx*), African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*), gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*), and Maasai giraffe (*Giraffa tippelskirchi*). Birdlife was also abundant, with sightings of secretary birds (*Sagittarius serpentarius*), tawny eagles (*Aquila rapax*), kori bustards (*Ardeotis kori*), white-bellied bustards (*Lissotis albiventris*), and several shrike species.

Near Aruba Dam, wildlife activity was concentrated around water points. Elephants were observed bathing and playing, while a hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibius*) rested in shallow water. Plains zebra and a blue wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus*) grazed nearby, and large numbers of herons, ducks, and storks were present. As we departed the water point toward Aruba Dam, a large flock of red-billed queleas (*Quelea quelea*) rose suddenly into the air, forming dense, swirling flocks. A Nile monitor lizard (*Varanus niloticus*) crossed the road shortly thereafter.

At Aruba Dam, multiple raptors were observed soaring overhead, including lappet-faced vultures (*Torgos tracheliotos*), tawny eagles, and two additional eagle species that could not be identified with certainty. Reports from park staff indicated a recent lion kill in the area, likely explaining the high raptor activity. On the ground, elephants, impalas, zebras, waterbuck (*Kobus ellipsiprymnus*), and hartebeests congregated around the dam. Along the water's edge, approximately 50 black herons (*Egretta ardesiaca*) were recorded, many displaying their characteristic umbrella-shading feeding behavior.

Approaching Voi Gate, a banded mongoose (*Mungos mungo*) was observed perched on a roadside sign. Troops of yellow baboons (*Papio cynocephalus*) and vervet monkeys (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*) were active near the visitor center, interacting with tourists and scavenging around facilities. Just beyond the park boundary, the day concluded with observations of elephants browsing near the fence, providing a fitting close to a journey that spanned Kenya's coastal ecosystems to the semi-arid savannas of Tsavo East.

Mammals observed

1. Common warthog (*Phacochoerus africanus*; Least Concern) – Several individuals observed in the park
2. Kirk's dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*; Least Concern) – Several individuals observed on the stretch between Makongeni and Sala Gate, as well as inside the park
3. Gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*; Near Threatened) – Several individuals observed in the park
4. Vervet monkey (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*; Least Concern) – Observed at Voi Gate
5. Yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*; Least Concern) – Observed at Voi Gate
6. Masai giraffe (*Giraffa tippelskirchi*; **Endangered**) – Approximately 10 individuals observed within the park
7. African buffalo (*Syncerus caffer*; Least Concern) – Two groups observed in the park
8. Impala (*Aepyceros melampus*; Least Concern) – Several individuals observed across the park
9. Grant's gazelle (*Nanger granti*; Least Concern) – Several individuals observed in the park
10. Unstriped ground squirrel (*Xerus rutilus*; Least Concern) – Observed near Aruba Dam
11. Hartebeest (*Alcelaphus buselaphus*; Least Concern) – Several individuals observed in the park
12. Fringe-eared oryx (*Oryx beisa callotis*; **Vulnerable**) – Three groups observed in the park
13. Blue wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus*; Least Concern) – One individual observed at the watering point near the lodge before Aruba Dam
14. African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*; **Endangered**) – At least 6 groups observed in the park
15. Plains zebra (*Equus quagga*; Near Threatened) – Several individuals observed across the park
16. Lion (*Panthera leo*; **Vulnerable**) – A pride with a kill was observed by a tourist at Aruba Dam
17. Banded mongoose (*Mungos mungo*; Least Concern) – A group observed near the Makongeni stretch and another near Voi Gate
18. Hirola (*Beatragus hunteri*; **Critically Endangered**) – Reported to occur within park

Figure 21: Entrance to Tsavo East National Park at Sala Gate, marking a clear transition from the coastal-influenced landscape to drier grassland and bushland dominated by *Acacia* and *Commiphora* species. The vegetation structure reflects semi-arid conditions characteristic of the eastern Tsavo ecosystem.

Figure 22: Degraded habitat just inside Sala Gate, Tsavo East National Park, characterized by extensive bare ground and scattered white flame trees (*Delonix elata*) showing heavy browsing and dieback. The vegetation structure reflects prolonged drought conditions combined with intense herbivory at the park's eastern boundary.

Figure 23: A white-flowered flame tree (*Delonix elata*) approximately 30 km inside Tsavo East National Park from Sala Gate, supporting multiple bird nests within its canopy. A snake eagle (family *Accipitridae*) was observed perched at the crown of the tree, illustrating the importance of mature trees as nesting and hunting perches within open savanna and bushland habitats.

Figure 24: A fringe-eared (Beisa) oryx (*Oryx beisa callotis*) observed browsing on dry twigs within open, arid grassland interspersed with large termite mounds in Tsavo East National Park. This subspecies is distinguished from the northern Beisa oryx (*Oryx beisa beisa*) by a pronounced black flank stripe and characteristic black ear tufts, features that give rise to the common name “fringe-eared oryx.”

Figure 25: A male and female gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*) observed foraging within arid bushland, displaying sex-specific feeding postures. The female was recorded standing upright on her hind legs to browse higher Acacia foliage, while the male fed on lower branches. This characteristic behavior reflects the species' specialized browsing strategy and underlies the common name "giraffe gazelle."

Figure 26: African elephants (*Loxodonta africana*) drinking at a water point near Aruba Dam in Tsavo East National Park. Nearby, plains zebra (*Equus quagga*), hartebeest (*Alcelaphus buselaphus*), and a blue wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus*) were observed around the water's edge. The site also supported a diverse assemblage of waterbirds, including African spoonbills (*Platalea alba*), knob-billed ducks (*Sarkidiornis melanotos*), black-headed herons (*Ardea melanocephala*), black storks (*Ciconia nigra*), sacred ibises (*Threskiornis aethiopicus*), and Egyptian geese (*Alopochen aegyptiaca*), highlighting the importance of artificial and natural water points in sustaining wildlife during dry conditions.

Figure 27: A hippopotamus (*Hippopotamus amphibius*) resting partially submerged in shallow water near Aruba Dam, with only the eyes and ears visible above the surface. A black-headed heron (*Ardea melanocephala*) was observed nearby along the water's edge in Tsavo East National Park.

Figure 28: A large flock of red-billed queleas (*Quelea quelea*) descending onto grassland in Tsavo East National Park. A Nile monitor lizard (*Varanus niloticus*) was observed feeding on queleas that had fallen following collisions during the dense flocking event, illustrating predator-prey interactions associated with mass avian movements in open savanna habitats.

Figure 29: A lappet-faced vulture (*Torgos tracheliotos*; IUCN: Endangered) perched alongside a tawny eagle (*Aquila rapax*) near Aruba Dam in Tsavo East National Park. The tawny eagle was observed preening, while the vulture remained stationary. As a large obligate scavenger, the lappet-faced vulture plays an important ecological role in carcass removal but faces ongoing threats from poisoning, habitat degradation, and human–wildlife conflict.

Figure 30: Left: Dense grassland and bushland habitat within Tsavo East National Park, supporting large herbivores including the fringe-eared oryx (*Oryx beisa callotis*; IUCN: Vulnerable). Right: Desert warthogs (*Phacochoerus aethiopicus*) observed at Galana Ranch, outside Tsavo East National Park and some distance from Sala Gate, illustrating the presence of arid-adapted mammals across the broader Tsavo–Galana landscape.

Day 5, 2 June: Voi-Tsavo West National Park

After completing our transect drive through Tsavo East National Park toward Voi, we continued with an evening drive to Tsavo West National Park. The route passed through several towns and offered expansive views of the Taita Hills, a montane system renowned for its high biodiversity and exceptional levels of endemism, with some species restricted to individual hills. These hills form an important ecological contrast to the surrounding semi-arid lowlands and are recognized as a key conservation landscape in southeastern Kenya.

By the time we entered Tsavo West National Park, night had already fallen, limiting visibility and reducing opportunities for wildlife observation. As a result, only a small number of mammals were recorded during the night drive, most notably Maasai giraffes (*Giraffa tippelskirchi*) observed intermittently along the roadside.

Mammals observed

1. Masai giraffe (*Giraffa tippelskirchi*; **Endangered**) – 2 individuals observed within the park
2. Common warthog (*Phacochoerus africanus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
3. Kirk's dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
4. Gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*; Near Threatened) – Reported to occur within park
5. Yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
6. African buffalo (*Syncerus caffer*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
7. Impala (*Aepyceros melampus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
8. Grant's gazelle (*Nanger granti*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
9. Hartebeest (*Alcelaphus buselaphus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
10. Fringe-eared oryx (*Oryx beisa callotis*; **Vulnerable**) – Reported to occur within park
11. African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*; **Endangered**) – Reported to occur within park
12. Plains zebra (*Equus quagga*; Near Threatened) – Reported to occur within park
13. Lion (*Panthera leo*; **Vulnerable**) – Reported to occur within park
14. Blue wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
15. Lesser kudu (*Tragelaphus imberbis*; Near Threatened) – Reported to occur within park
16. Waterbuck (*Kobus ellipsiprymnus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
17. Black-backed jackal (*Lupulella mesomelas*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park
18. Steenbok (*Raphicerus campestris*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park

19. Common eland (*Taurotragus oryx*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within park

Day 6, 3 June: Voi-Nairobi

The final day of the expedition began with a morning session focused on reflection and planning. Participants discussed strategies for sustaining collaborations, expanding wildlife education outreach to schools, and provided feedback on the expedition, highlighting key learning experiences as well as suggestions for improving future training courses.

Following these discussions, we departed Voi and travelled back to Nairobi, passing through landscapes dominated by bushland, woodland, and open grasslands. Although the return journey traversed habitats known to support diverse wildlife, observations were incidental as the primary focus of the day was travel and consolidation of outcomes from the expedition.

Mammals observed

1. Masai giraffe (*Giraffa tippelskirchi*; **Endangered**) – 10 individuals observed at Kapiti plains, 2 individuals observed in Voi (Tsavo East National Park), reported to occur in Malili and Emali
2. Yellow baboon (*Papio cynocephalus*; Least Concern) – 16 individuals observed near Tsavo River after Manyani (Tsavo West National Park), reported to occur in Voi (Tsavo East National Park), Kiunduan (Tsavo West National Park)
3. Plains zebra (*Equus quagga*; Near Threatened) – 6 individuals observed in Voi (Tsavo East National Park), 20 individuals observed at Mbololo (Tsavo East National Park), 8 individuals observed at Manyani (Tsavo West National Park), 3 individuals observed at Malili, 7 individuals observed at Konza
4. Impala (*Aepyceros melampus*; Least Concern) – 10 individuals observed at Kapiti plains, reported to occur at Irima (Tsavo East National Park)
5. Spotted hyaena (*Crocuta crocuta*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur at Voi in Tsavo East National Park
6. Cheetah (*Acinonyx jubatus*; **Vulnerable**) – Reported to occur at Irima in Tsavo East National Park
7. Lion (*Panthera leo*; **Vulnerable**) – Reported to occur at Irima in Tsavo East National Park
8. Common warthog (*Phacochoerus africanus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within Tsavo East National Park at Mbololo

9. Kirk's dik-dik (*Madoqua kirkii*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within Tsavo East National Park at Mbololo
10. Rock hyrax (*Procavia capensis*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur within Tsavo East National Park at Mbololo
11. African elephant (*Loxodonta africana*; **Endangered**) – 3 individuals observed within Tsavo East National Park at Kyulu
12. Grant's gazelle (*Nanger granti*; Least Concern) – 20 individuals observed at Malili, reported to occur at Voi (Tsavo East National Park)
13. Common eland (*Taurotragus oryx*; Least Concern) – 11 individuals observed at Malili
14. Blue wildebeest (*Connochaetes taurinus*; Least Concern) – 10 individuals observed in Malili
15. Thomson's gazelle (*Eudorcas thomsonii*; Least Concern) – 10 individuals observed in Malili
16. Aardvark (*Orycteropus afer*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur in Malili
17. Striped ground squirrel (*Xerus erythropus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur in Emali
18. Unstriped ground squirrel (*Xerus rutilus*; Least Concern) – Roadkill at Kiunduani
19. Vervet monkey (*Chlorocebus pygerythrus*; Least Concern) – Reported to occur in Emali and Kiunduani
20. Gerenuk (*Litocranius walleri*; Near Threatened) – 2 individuals observed in Athi Kapiti plains
21. Hartebeest (*Alcelaphus buselaphus*; Least Concern) – 6 individuals observed in Athi Kapiti plains

Table 1: Mammal species records documented during the North Coast Kenya expedition and along the Mombasa Road corridor (Voi to Athi Kapiti Plains), showing IUCN Red List status, observation-level counts by location, and associated habitat descriptions.

NO.	COMMON NAME	SCIENTIFIC NAME	IUCN STATUS	NUMBER OBSERVED	LOCATION	HABITAT
ORDER: PROBOSCIDEA						
1	African savanna elephant	<i>Loxodonta africana</i>	Endangered	Fresh dung	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				3	Kyulu (Tsavo West National Park)	Grassland
				Fresh dung	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
				≥6 groups	Tsavo East National Park	Semi-arid savanna
ORDER: TUBULIDENTATA						
2	Aardvark	<i>Orycteropus afer</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Malili	Savanna-bushland mosaic
ORDER: MACROSCELIDEA						
3	Golden-rumped sengi	<i>Rhynchocyon chrysopygus</i>	Endangered	1	Gede Ruins Forest	Coastal forest
ORDER: HYRACOIDEA						
4	Rock hyrax	<i>Procavia capensis</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Mbololo (Tsavo East)	Savanna
ORDER: PRIMATES						
5	Tana River mangabey	<i>Cercocebus galeritus</i>	Critically Endangered	3 groups (6,5,4)	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
6	Tana River red colobus	<i>Piliocolobus rufomitratu</i>	Critically Endangered	4	Lake Ishaqbini	Riverine forest
				~12	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
7	Coastal Sykes' monkey	<i>Cercopithecus mitis albotorquatus</i>	Vulnerable	8	Lake Ishaqbini	Riverine forest
				5	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
8	Sykes monkey	<i>Cercopithecus mitis</i>	Least Concern	~15	Gede Ruins Forest	Coastal forest

				Reported presence	Mida Creek	Mangrove islands
9	Vervet monkey	<i>Chlorocebus pygerythrus</i>	Least Concern	Observed	Emali; Kiunduani	Grassland
				5	Garsen–Hola Road	Semi-arid bushland
				~10	Gede Ruins entrance	Coastal forest
				~10	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				5	Kotile–Lazima	Thorn scrub
				Mostly at entrance	Mida Creek	Mangrove edge
				8	Voi Gate (Tsavo East)	Park edge
10	Somali lesser galago	<i>Galago gallarum</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
11	Senegal lesser galago	<i>Galago senegalensis</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				Reported presence	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
12	Small-eared galago	<i>Otolemur garnettii</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
13	Northern greater galago-lasiotis	<i>Otolemur garnettii lasiotis</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
14	Yellow baboon	<i>Papio cynocephalus</i>	Least Concern	40	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				7	Lazima	River floodplains
				16	Manyani (Tsavo West)	Grassland
				Mostly on islands	Mida Creek	Mangrove islands
				2 troops	Road to Masalani	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				10	Voi Gate (Tsavo East)	Park edge
15	Kenya coast galago	<i>Paragalago cocos</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest

ORDER: CARNIVORA						
16	Cheetah	<i>Acinonyx jubatus</i>	Vulnerable	Reported presence	Tsavo East	Grassland
17	Lion	<i>Panthera leo</i>	Vulnerable	Reported presence	Ishaqbini Conservancy	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				Pride (kill site)	Tsavo East (Aruba Dam)	Semi-arid savanna
				Reported presence	Tsavo West & Tsavo East (Irima)	Grassland
18	Leopard	<i>Panthera pardus</i>	Vulnerable	Reported presence	Ishaqbini Conservancy	Savanna-bushland mosaic
19	Striped hyaena	<i>Hyaena hyaena</i>	Near Threatened	1 (roadkill)	Beneneka	Thorn bushland
20	Marsh mongoose	<i>Atilax paludinosus</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Mida Creek	Mangrove wetlands
21	African civet	<i>Civettictis civetta</i>	Least Concern	1 roadkill; 1 remains	Kafi-Hola Junction	Thorn bushland
				Reported presence	Mida Creek	Mangrove islands
22	Spotted hyaena	<i>Crocuta crocuta</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Voi (Tsavo East)	Savanna
23	Common genet	<i>Genetta genetta</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
24	Large spotted genet	<i>Genetta maculata</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
25	Somali dwarf mongoose	<i>Helogale hirtula</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				~7	Kotile	Savanna-bushland
26	White-tailed mongoose	<i>Ichneumia albicauda</i>	Least Concern	1	Garissa Town	Urban settlement
				Reported presence	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
27	Black-backed jackal	<i>Lupulella mesomelas</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic

				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
28	Banded mongoose	<i>Mungos mungo</i>	Least Concern	5	Makongeni (Tsavo segment)	Roadside bushland
				2	Voi Gate (Tsavo)	Rock pile
ORDER: PERISSODACTYLA						
29	Plains zebra	<i>Equus quagga</i>	Near Threatened	Observed	Athi Kapiti, Mbololo, Manyani, Konza, Malili	Grassland / Savanna-bushland
				Observed	En route to Ishaqbini	Savannah
				Observed	Kotile	Semi-arid woodland
				3	Masalani	Urban semi-arid bushland
				Several	Tsavo East National Park	Savannah
				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
ORDER: ARTIODACTYLA						
30	Hirola	<i>Beatragus hunteri</i>	Critically Endangered	7	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
31	Coastal topi	<i>Damaliscus lunatus topi</i>	Endangered	2 groups (5 & 7)	Near Kotile	Semi-arid woodland
32	Reticulated giraffe	<i>Giraffa reticulata</i>	Endangered	~15	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				~5	Near Kotile	Semi-arid woodland
33	Masai giraffe	<i>Giraffa tippelskirchi</i>	Endangered	10	Athi Kapiti Plains	Grassland
				Reported presence	Malili and Emali	Semi-arid savanna
				~15	Tsavo East National Park	Semi-arid savanna
				2	Tsavo West National Park	Semi-arid savanna
34	Hippopotamus	<i>Hippopotamus amphibius</i>	Vulnerable	2	Near Aruba Dam	Wetland
				5	Tana River at TRPR	River

35	Fringe-eared oryx	<i>Oryx beisa callotis</i>	Vulnerable	3 groups	Tsavo East National Park	Semi-arid savanna
				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
36	Gerenuk	<i>Litocranius walleri</i>	Near Threatened	2	Athi Kapiti Plains	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				~15	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				2	Kotile	Thorn scrub
				27	Tsavo East National Park	Semi-arid savanna
37	African buffalo	<i>Syncerus caffer</i>	Near Threatened	Fresh tracks	Lake Ishaqbini	Savannah, floodplain
				2 groups (5 & 4)	Tsavo East National Park	Savannah
38	Lesser kudu	<i>Tragelaphus imberbis</i>	Near Threatened	4	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
39	Impala	<i>Aepyceros melampus</i>	Least Concern	10	Athi Kapiti Plains	Grassland
				Reported presence	Irima (Tsavo West)	Grassland
				~30	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				~20	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
				~60	Tsavo East National Park	Savannah
40	Hartebeest	<i>Alcelaphus buselaphus</i>	Least Concern	6	Athi Kapiti Plains	Grassland
				~15	Tsavo East National Park	Grassland
				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
41	Blue wildebeest	<i>Connochaetes taurinus</i>	Least Concern	10	Malili	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				1	Tsavo East National Park	Grassland

				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
42	Waterbuck	<i>Kobus ellipsiprymnus</i>	Least Concern	~15	Aruba Dam (Tsavo East)	Riparian / wetland edge
				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Riparian / wetland edge
43	Kirk's dik-dik	<i>Madoqua kirkii</i>	Least Concern	~30	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				~5	Kotile	Savanna bushland
				Several	Makongeni–Sala Gate	Semi-arid bushland
				~5	Tana River Primate Reserve	Semi-arid bushland
				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
44	Grant's gazelle	<i>Nanger granti</i>	Least Concern	11	Malili	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				~40	Tsavo East National Park	Grassland
				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
45	Desert warthog	<i>Phacochoerus aethiopicus</i>	Least Concern	~20	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				6	Masalani Town	Urban semi-arid bushland
46	Common warthog	<i>Phacochoerus africanus</i>	Least Concern	Several	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				Several	Tsavo East National Park	Semi-arid savannah
				Reported presence	Tsavo West & Mbololo	Grassland
				10	Tula-Bura Tana	Savannah
47	Steenbok	<i>Raphicerus campestris</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
48	Common eland	<i>Taurotragus oryx</i>	Least Concern	11	Malili	Savanna-bushland mosaic

				Reported presence	Tsavo West	Grassland
49	Bushbuck	<i>Tragelaphus scriptus</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Mida Creek	Mangrove islands
				Tracks observed	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
ORDER: LAGOMORPHA						
50	Cape hare	<i>Lepus capensis</i>	Least Concern	1 (roadkill)	Kafi–HOLA Junction	Roadside
ORDER: RODENTIA						
51	Black-tailed gerbil	<i>Gerbilliscus nigricaudus</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Ishaqbini Sanctuary	Savanna-bushland mosaic
52	Red-bellied coast squirrel	<i>Paraxerus palliatus tanae</i>	Least Concern	1	Tana River Primate Reserve	Riverine forest
53	Striped ground squirrel	<i>Xerus erythropus</i>	Least Concern	Reported presence	Emali	Savanna
54	Unstriped ground squirrel	<i>Xerus rutilus</i>	Least Concern	1	HOLA	Thorn bushland
				Reported presence	Ishaqbini	Savanna-bushland mosaic
				Roadkill	Kiunduani	Grassland
				1	Tsavo East near Aruba Dam	Grassland
ORDER: EULIPOTYPHILA						
55	White-bellied hedgehog	<i>Atelerix albiventris</i>	Least Concern	2	Gede Ruins Forest	Coastal forest

TRAINING AND CAPACITY BUILDING

An integral component of the mammal-focused expedition was a structured training program designed to build capacity among early-career researchers and students interested in mammalogy and wildlife conservation. Training activities were embedded within daily fieldwork and delivered through hands-on, experiential learning across the diverse habitats encountered during the expedition. This approach ensured that participants gained practical skills in real-world contexts while engaging directly with conservation challenges on the ground.

Course description: The field-based training program functioned as an embedded course within the broader expedition framework. Participants received guided instruction and practical experience in mammal identification, field survey techniques, behavioral observation, data management, and conservation communication. Emphasis was placed on applying scientific concepts in situ, integrating ecological understanding with practical skills and citizen science tools. The training adopted a multidisciplinary perspective, linking mammalogy with conservation practice, community engagement, and biodiversity data sharing.

Course Goals and Pedagogical Foundations: The overarching goal of the training was to strengthen practical capacity in mammal research and conservation while fostering scientific thinking, adaptability, and professional development. Specifically, the program aimed to:

- Build proficiency in mammal identification using morphology, behavior, habitat cues, and indirect signs.
- Introduce and apply appropriate mammal detection and documentation methods across diverse ecosystems.
- Enhance understanding of conservation challenges facing mammals in Kenya.
- Promote standardized biodiversity data collection and contribution to citizen science platforms, including MaKenya and iNaturalist.
- Develop skills in diagnostic field photography and systematic data recording.
- Strengthen communication and outreach competencies relevant to conservation education.
- Cultivate resilience, adaptability, and effective problem-solving in fieldwork settings.

- Encourage a scientific mindset grounded in curiosity, observation, and analytical thinking.

Pedagogical Approach: The training relied on experiential and participatory learning, combining guided instruction, peer learning, real-time problem solving, and reflective discussion. Instruction emphasized inquiry-based learning and collaborative knowledge building, allowing participants to actively engage with ecological processes and conservation issues as they unfolded in the field. Learning was context-sensitive, drawing directly from observations, encounters with wildlife, and interactions with conservation practitioners and local communities.

Core competency areas:

1. Mammal Identification Techniques

Participants were trained to identify mammals using physical characteristics, behavioral cues, habitat associations, and indirect evidence such as tracks, scats, feeding signs, and vocalizations. Taxonomic knowledge was reinforced through discussion of species distributions and ecological niches.

2. Field Survey and Detection Methods

Training covered a range of survey techniques, including road transects, line transects, and opportunistic searches. Emphasis was placed on selecting and adapting methods based on target taxa, habitat structure, and environmental conditions.

3. Conservation Challenges and Threat Assessment

Participants engaged in critical assessments of conservation pressures through direct habitat observation, discussions with local communities, and dialogue with conservation professionals. This fostered an understanding of anthropogenic impacts, habitat degradation, and species-specific threats.

4. Citizen Science and Data Sharing

Trainees received practical instruction on contributing high-quality records to national and global biodiversity platforms i.e., MaKenya mobile app and iNaturalist. Sessions

focused on accurate species identification, georeferencing, metadata standards, and ethical data sharing.

5. Field Photography and Documentation

Guidance was provided on capturing clear, diagnostic photographs suitable for research, monitoring, and citizen science applications.

6. Conservation Outreach and Education

Discussions explored the role of outreach in mammal conservation, particularly through engagement with schools, local communities, and higher education institutions.

Participants considered strategies for effective conservation communication tailored to different audiences.

7. Field Planning and Resilience

Training addressed logistical planning, teamwork, and adaptive strategies for managing challenges such as difficult terrain, weather variability, and equipment limitations.

8. Developing a Scientific Mindset

Participants were encouraged to approach fieldwork with curiosity, rigor, and creativity, learning to frame ecological questions and think critically about conservation problems and solutions.

9. Data Recording and Field Notes

Emphasis was placed on standardized data collection, including recording species counts, age structure, behavior, GPS coordinates, habitat descriptions, and observation timing.

10. Behavioral Observations

Participants practiced observing and interpreting mammalian behavior, including foraging strategies, social interactions, vigilance, movement patterns, and responses to disturbance.

Training outcomes: Overall, the training program provided an immersive learning experience that strengthened practical skills, ecological understanding, and scientific capacity among emerging mammalogists. Beyond individual development, the training contributed to broader

conservation goals by equipping participants with the tools to document biodiversity, engage communities, and support evidence-based conservation of Kenya's mammalian fauna.

Table 2: Field itinerary and associated training topics conducted during the mammal expedition, showing daily travel segments, instructional focus areas, key activities, and facilitators.

DAY	SEGMENT	TRAINING FOCUS	KEY ACTIVITIES	INSTRUCTOR / FACILITATOR
1	Nairobi → Garissa	Field preparation and expectations	Safety briefing; clarification of team roles and expedition objectives; road-transect observations; introductory mammal identification; habitat recognition and discussion of conservation challenges	Drive-and-talk led by Leo Khasoha , John Kabue , and Simon Musila on expedition expectations, mammal identification, and conservation context
2–3	Garissa → Ishaqbini Hirola Community Conservancy	Community engagement in conservation; mammal identification techniques	Informal interviews with local community members to document human–wildlife interactions, identify threats, and explore community-based conservation initiatives; mammal identification using morphology and distribution ranges with field guides	Informal briefing with Ishaqbini Conservancy Management ; drive-and-talk with Aden Elmi (Head of Research, Ishaqbini Conservancy) on hirola conservation
4	Ishaqbini Conservancy → Kotile → Lazima → Garsen → Tana River Primate National Reserve	Survey design and detection methods; habitat assessment	Detection methods based on animal behavior, tracks and signs, habitat structure, and geographic distribution; identification of conservation challenges across habitat gradients	Drive-and-talk with Leo Khasoha , John Kabue , and Simon Musila ; walk-and-talk with Charles Maingi on conservation of the Critically Endangered Tana River mangabey and Tana River red colobus

5	Garsen → Malindi → Mida Creek → Gede Ruins	Field photography; citizen science; data ethics	Structured observation sessions documenting behavior and species interactions with photographic records; uploading observations to iNaturalist and MaKenya; location tagging and quality control	Informal briefing with Mida Creek management on conservation and community empowerment; walk-and-talk with Mwaringa Saha on the Kipepeo (Butterfly) Project; walk-and-talk with Leo Khasoha, John Kabue, and Simon Musila on mammal sampling with emphasis on sengis; informal lecture by Simon Musila on citizen science, wildlife photography, MaKenya/iNaturalist use, and publishing
6	Malindi → Tsavo East (Sala Gate–Voi) → Tsavo West National Park	Adaptive field techniques; savanna conservation challenges	Habitat identification; savanna transects; adapting survey methods by species and habitat; team-based data collection	Drive-and-talk with Leo Khasoha, John Kabue, and Simon Musila on mammal identification and conservation challenges
7	Voi → Nairobi	Conservation project development; scientific thinking; collaboration	Group discussions on project idea development; identifying collaboration opportunities; reflection on skills gained and future conservation or research pathways	Informal session led by Leo Khasoha, John Kabue, and Simon Musila focusing on project design, collaboration, and participant feedback

Figure 31: Dr. Simon Musila (left), a mammalogist at the National Museums of Kenya and expedition instructor, leading a training session on biodiversity data mapping and sharing using the MaKenya platform and iNaturalist. The session demonstrated how iNaturalist supports species identification through a global network of contributors and formed part of the expedition's hands-on training in data collection, citizen science, and conservation communication.

Figure 32: Left: Primate researcher Charles Maingi engages the expedition team within the Tana River Primate National Reserve, sharing insights from his long-term research on the endemic and Critically Endangered Tana River mangabey (*Cercocebus galeritus*) and Tana River red colobus (*Piliocolobus rufomitratu*), including their behavior, foraging ecology, and conservation threats. Right: Expedition participants scan the forest canopy with binoculars while recording observations using the MaKenya Mammal App and iNaturalist during their first encounters with these rare primates.

Figure 33: Students practice wildlife photography techniques for citizen science using a white-bellied hedgehog (*Atelerix albiventris*) encountered in a coastal forest patch at Gede Ruins. The session emphasized the importance of clear, well-composed images for accurate species identification and effective biodiversity data sharing through platforms such as iNaturalist and MaKenya.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This expedition successfully integrated field-based training, biodiversity documentation, and conservation engagement across under-sampled landscapes of northern coastal Kenya. By combining opportunistic surveys with structured data recording, the expedition generated valuable occurrence records for 55 mammal species across a wide range of habitats, including several globally threatened and endemic taxa. Notable records of the Critically Endangered hirola, Tana River mangabey, and Tana River red colobus, as well as the Endangered coastal topi and reticulated giraffe, contribute directly to national biodiversity mapping and long-term conservation planning efforts in Kenya (Groom & Western, 2013; Muehlenbein, 2010).

Beyond data generation, the expedition demonstrated the importance of experiential, field-based training in building local capacity for mammal research and conservation. Hands-on instruction in species identification, survey methods, data management, and citizen science platforms equipped early-career researchers with practical skills essential for biodiversity monitoring in data-poor regions. Such capacity-building is especially critical in landscapes experiencing rapid ecological change due to infrastructure development, agricultural expansion, invasive species, and climate variability. The expedition also highlighted the

central role of community-led conservation in sustaining threatened species outside formally protected areas. Initiatives observed at Ishaqbini Hirola Community Conservancy and Mida Creek illustrate how locally driven stewardship can complement national conservation frameworks and enhance the persistence of vulnerable wildlife populations.

While the survey was limited by its short duration and opportunistic sampling design, the records generated provide important baseline information and underscore the value of repeat surveys and long-term monitoring in these regions. Continued support for similar multidisciplinary expeditions will be essential for closing biodiversity data gaps, strengthening conservation partnerships, and training the next generation of Kenyan mammalogists and conservation practitioners.

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REFERENCES

- Ali, A.H., Kauffman, M.J., Amin, R., Kibara, A., King, J., Mallon, D., Musyoki, C. & Goheen, J.R. (2018). Demographic drivers of a refugee species: large-scale experiments guide strategies for reintroductions of hirola. *Ecological Applications*, 28, 275–283.
- Andanje, S.A., Ottichilo, W.K., Malakwen, J.M. & Seno, S.O. (2011). Hirola *Beatragus hunteri* Conservation and Management Action Plan 2012–2016. Kenya Wildlife Service, Nairobi.
- Beentje, H.J. (1994). Kenya Trees, Shrubs and Lianas. National Museums of Kenya, Nairobi.
- BirdLife International (2023). Important Bird Areas factsheet: Mida Creek. Available at: <http://www.birdlife.org> (accessed 19 August 2025).
- Bonney, R., Phillips, T. B., Ballard, H. L. & Enck, J. W. (2016). Can citizen science enhance public understanding of science?, *Public Understanding of Science*, 25(1), 2–16.
- Bosire, J.O., Dahdouh-Guebas, F., Kairo, J.G. & Koedam, N. (2006). Success rates of transplanted mangrove trees in Kenya. *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 325, 85–91.
- Butynski, T.M. & de Jong, Y. (2019). Status and conservation of the Tana River primates. *Primate Conservation*, 33, 45–58.
- Butynski, T.M. & Hamerlynck, O. (2016). Impacts of the High Grand Falls Dam on Lower Tana biodiversity. *Journal of East African Natural History*, 105, 1–12.
- Butynski, T.M. & Mwangi, G. (1994). Conservation status and distribution of the Tana River red colobus and crested mangabey. Report, Zoo Atlanta, Nairobi.
- Butynski, T.M. (2000). Africa's endangered hirola antelope: status and conservation. *Gnusletter*, 19, 6–8.
- Dagg, A.I. (2014). Giraffe: Biology, Behaviour and Conservation. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- East, R. (1999). African Antelope Database 1998. IUCN/SSC Antelope Specialist Group, IUCN, Gland & Cambridge.

- FAO (n.d.) Useful Trees and Shrubs for Kenya: *Dobera glabra* profile. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome.
- Fashing, P. J., Muldoon, K. M., Chapman, C. A., Davenport, T. R. B., De Jong, Y. A. & Butynski, T. M. (2014). Mammals of the Mount Kenya and Aberdare Mountains, *African Journal of Ecology*, 52(2), 155–167.
- Groom, R., Western, D. & Said, M. (2012). The impact of land subdivision and sedentarization of pastoral communities on wildlife in an African savanna ecosystem. *Biological Conservation*, 142, 253–265.
- Groom, R.J. & Western, D. (2013). Impact of land subdivision and sedentarization on wildlife in Kenya's southern rangelands. *Rangeland Ecology & Management*, 66, 1–9.
- Hamerlynck, O., Nyunja, J., Luke, Q. & Waweru, C. (2012). Hydrological threats to Tana River forests. *Hydrobiologia*, 708, 45–59.
- Howard, P. C., Davenport, T. R. B., Vhainan, A., Barnes, A. D. & Wright, J. (2017). Biodiversity and conservation status of Kenya's coastal forests, *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 26(2), pp. 423–439.
- iNaturalist (2023). iNaturalist platform overview. Available at: <https://www.inaturalist.org/pages/about> (accessed 19 August 2025).
- IUCN Red List (2024). *Cercocebus galeritus* (Tana River Mangabey). Available at: <https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/136363/17985635> (accessed 19 August 2025).
- IUCN Red List (2024). *Ptilocolobus rufomitratu*s (Tana River Red Colobus). Available at: <https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/13599/17973285> (accessed 19 August 2025).
- IUCN SSC Afrotheria Specialist Group (2016). *Rhynchocyon chrysopygus*. *The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2016*. <https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2016-3.RLTS.T41515A45187668.en> (accessed 19 August 2025).
- IUCN SSC Antelope Specialist Group (2016). *Damaliscus lunatus ssp. topi*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2016: e.T136613A50195097. Available at: <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2016-3.RLTS.T136613A50195097.en> (accessed 19 August 2025).

- Kairo, J.G., Kiviyatu, B. & Koedam, N. (2002). Application of remote sensing and GIS in the management of mangrove forests within and adjacent to Kiunga Marine Protected Area, Kenya. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 45, 829–844.
- Kenya Wildlife Service (KWS) (2020). Priority ecosystems and species. Available at: <https://www.kws.go.ke/content/priority-ecosystems-and-species> (accessed 19 August 2025).
- Maingi, C.K. & Kivai, S.M. (2007). Human and natural impacts on forests along Lower Tana River, Kenya: implications towards conservation and management of endemic primate species and their habitat. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 16, 1063–1079.
- Maingi, C.K. & Marsh, S.E. (2002). Quantifying hydrologic impacts following dam construction along the Tana River, Kenya. *Journal of Arid Environments*, 50, 53–79.
- Maingi, C.K. & Marsh, S.E. (2006). Composition, structure, and regeneration patterns in a gallery forest along the Tana River near Bura, Kenya. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 236, 211–221.
- Maingi, C.K. (2019). Forest fragmentation and anthropogenic disturbance: implications on plant foods and behavior of the Tana River mangabey (*Cercocebus galeritus*). PhD thesis, University of Nairobi, Kenya.
- Maingi, C.K., Githaiga, J.M., Kanya, J.I. & Kivai, S.M. (2020). Anthropogenic activities and influence on behavior of the Tana River mangabey (*Cercocebus galeritus*) in two forest fragments in Lower Tana River, Kenya. *African Primates*, 14, 21–34.
- Maingi, C.K., Mutua, J., Musyoka, R. & Kivai, S.M. (2020). Land cover changes in the Lower Tana River. *African Journal of Ecology*, 58, 540–552.
- Measham, T.G. & Lumbasi, J. (2013). Success factors for community-based natural resource management (CBNRM): lessons from Kenya and Australia. *Scopus: Journal of East African Ornithology*, 28, 1–14.
- Muehlenbein, M.P. (ed.) (2010). Human–wildlife interaction: emerging infectious diseases and the conservation of biodiversity. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Muneza, A.B., Doherty, J.B., Hussein, A.A., Hussein, N. & Fennessy, J. (2018). Giraffa camelopardalis ssp. reticulata. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2018:

<https://doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2018-2.RLTS.T88420717A88420720.en> (accessed 19 August 2025).

- Mwangi, E., Magoma, G., Omondi, V. & Mwangi, M. (2019). Leveraging citizen science for mammal biodiversity mapping in Kenya' *African Journal of Ecology*, 57(4), 598–608.
- Mwangi, E., Mulundi, C. K., Nyaga, J. M. & Kariuki, B. W. (2016). Mammal diversity and conservation in Kenya: challenges and prospects, *Journal of East African Natural History*, 105(1), 1–15.
- Ramsay, M., Butynski, T. M. & Tyler, J. C. (2019). Ecology and behavior of the Kenya coast galago, *Primates*, 60(4), 285–294.
- Ruffo, C.K., Birnie, A. & Tengnäs, B. (2002). Edible wild plants of Tanzania. Regional Land Management Unit, Nairobi.
- Scofield, H., Ichonga, P. & Wambua, K. (2019). Human-wildlife conflict in Kenya: causes and mitigation strategies, *Conservation Science and Practice*, 1(3), e48.
- Sombroek, E., Makena, J. & Olwero, N. (2021). Connectivity and corridors in Kenya's landscapes: challenges and opportunities, *Landscape Ecology*, 36(7), 1789–1803.
- Struhsaker, T.T. & Grubb, P. (2013). Ecology and conservation of red colobus monkeys. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- UNEP (2020). Out of the Blue: the value of seagrasses to the environment and to people. *United Nations Environment Programme*, Nairobi.
- Western, D. (1973). The structure, dynamics and changes of the Amboseli ecosystem. *African Journal of Ecology*, 11, 307–325.
- Wieczkowski, J. & Butynski, T.M. (2013). Human–primate conflict in the Tana River region. *Primate Conservation*, 27, 123–131.
- Wieczkowski, J. (2005). Examination of the conservation status of the Tana River red colobus and crested mangabey. *International Journal of Primatology*, 26, 415–428.

PARTICIPANTS REFLECTIONS

Rowan Hadequ; Student at Chuka University attached at National Museums of Kenya)

“I joined the expedition to learn more about conservation efforts for endangered species and to actively engage in citizen science through mammal and bird mapping. The experience was incredibly motivating and well-organized, with passionate facilitators and a strong team spirit throughout the training.

During the expedition and course, I developed practical skills including species identification (birds and mammals), field navigation, leadership, teamwork, and wildlife photography for citizen science platforms like iNaturalist. I also gained a better

understanding of how biodiversity is linked to habitat and biomes.

This expedition greatly expanded my outlook on conservation and biodiversity research. It stirred creativity in planning future biodiversity-related projects and boosted my confidence in contributing meaningfully to community-based conservation. I recommend involving more students in future expeditions to increase awareness and impact. Including field guidebooks and ensuring a field expert is present at all times would further enhance the learning experience.”

Olivia Mukasia; Volunteer at Mammalogy Section – National Museums of Kenya

“I was selected by Dr. Simon Musila, Head of the Mammalogy Section, to participate in a specialized training on mammal identification and field sighting. This involved collecting and recording data using the MaKenya app—a tool used for mapping mammal distributions across Kenya.

Most of my previous experience had been with museum specimens, so this field-based training offered a refreshing and practical perspective. For example, I had previously only known of one giraffe species, but during the expedition I observed two of the three

Kenyan species in the wild: Reticulated and Masai giraffes. The training covered a range of habitats, starting in Garissa and continuing through Hola to Ishaqbini Conservancy, where we observed *Beatragus hunteri*. We then proceeded to Masalani and the Tana River Primate Reserve to see *Cercocebus galeritus* and *Procolobus rufomitratu*s, followed by a visit to Malindi and the Gedi Ruins to spot *Rhynchocyon chrysopygus*. We concluded the expedition in Tsavo East via Sala Gate, recording mammal sightings across forest, grassland, and arid ecosystems.

The experience with the organizers and fellow trainees was collaborative and inspiring. The organizers offered clear guidance and hands-on demonstrations, while the trainees were supportive and engaged, fostering strong teamwork and mutual respect. I gained practical skills in identifying mammals in the field, understanding their behavior, using mobile tools for citizen science, and interpreting species distributions across different ecological zones.

This expedition deepened my interest in mammal research and conservation. I am especially motivated to participate in initiatives that raise awareness at the community level and contribute to building conservation databases like MaKenya. I recommend involving more students in future courses to expand local expertise and enhance efforts to document and conserve Kenya’s rich mammalian biodiversity.”

Mercy W. Ndumia; Member of Mammal Committee of Nature Kenya

“As a member of the Mammal Committee, I joined the North Coast mammal expedition to step away from my daily routine and pursue something more purposeful. I wanted to get beyond the evening traffic and city lights and immerse myself in Kenya’s lesser-known mammalian landscapes. I saw this as an opportunity to challenge myself, explore hidden ecosystems, and contribute meaningfully to the conservation of our rare and endangered mammals.

One of the most memorable moments came at dawn in Ishaqbini, when we finally encountered the critically endangered Hirola (*Beatragus hunteri*) after searching for hours the previous evening without success. It felt like a huge victory. According to the conservancy’s head of research, the Hirola population currently stands at 68 individuals. He explained that because of the sanctuary’s fencing and very limited tourism, the animals have become extremely wary of vehicles, which made photographing them quite difficult. We also engaged with the conservancy management, who shared about their local conservation efforts. They described key initiatives such as supplementary feeding during droughts, employing local guides and rangers, bursary schemes for schoolchildren, and other economic empowerment programs. I was struck by how embedded the community is in the day-to-day work of conservation.

This expedition expanded my field skills—from traditional tracking and digital mapping to species identification and data recording. It also deepened my appreciation for how local communities are playing a central role in conservation. I now understand even more clearly how much work remains to be done: from filling species data gaps and preventing road mortality, to strengthening legal protections for unprotected taxa. Above all, I was reminded that some of Kenya’s most important conservation discoveries lie in the most unassuming places. Through this journey, I reaffirmed my commitment to wildlife conservation and look forward to supporting more expeditions that combine science, community, and heart.”

Lawrence Lonyil; Wildlife Control Officer at Kenya Airports Authority (KAA)

“I was honoured to participate in the Mammal Committee Training, having been nominated by Leo Khasoha after a conversation during the Nature Kenya AGM. As a Wildlife Control Officer, I am deeply invested in biodiversity monitoring around aviation zones, and this training aligned perfectly with both my professional responsibilities and personal interests.

The training was a truly engaging and enriching experience. The facilitators were professional, well-organized, and supportive throughout. I especially appreciated the collaborative spirit among participants from various institutions, which created an excellent environment for shared learning and mutual respect.

During the course, I gained several valuable and practical skills. I learned how to effectively use the Makenya App for recording and sharing mammal observations, how to correctly identify mammal species in the field using guides and observation techniques, and how to take clear, research-quality photographs of mammals for uploading to iNaturalist. These skills are already proving useful in my work, particularly in enhancing wildlife monitoring around airport environments where accurate data is vital for both aviation safety and biodiversity conservation.

For future training, I would recommend incorporating more hands-on fieldwork sessions, including overnight activities to better observe nocturnal species. Additionally, providing virtual refresher sessions after the training would help reinforce learning and maintain engagement over time.

I sincerely thank the organizers and the Mammal Committee for this opportunity. I look forward to applying the knowledge and skills gained in my current role and contributing meaningfully to future conservation efforts.”